

MADITRACE

Report on identification of related projects and activities

Deliverable D5.4

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Summary

This deliverable aims to produce a report through the analysis of the MaDiTraCe ecosystem and the research of related projects, initiatives, and events aligned with the main topics of the project.

A preliminary view that will facilitate to the partners the identification of venues for stablishing synergies and sharing knowledge with relevant stakeholders when a significant impact for the MaDiTraCe project results will be expected.

Keywords

Projects, synergies, traceability, transparency, sustainability, ecosystem, cooperation, stakeholders, DPP, CRM.

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
DPP	Digital Product Passport
GBA	Global Battery Alliance
ICT	Information & Communication Technology
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
Nb	Niobium
REE	Rare Earth Elements
TA	Tantalum
TBC	To Be Confirmed
TCE	Trichloroethylene
SLO	Social License to Operate
W	Tungsten
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to generate a report covering the projects and activities related to the MaDiTraCe project by engaging and exchanging information with other initiatives focusing on similar topics. The project aims to foster synergies among ongoing projects in coordination with all WP. This will be achieved through active participation in bilateral discussions and meetings, sharing results and deliverables, organising joint dissemination events, and participating in clustering activities with other European and national/regional projects. This is an ongoing task aimed at ensuring that selected and relevant outcomes from this project, as well as others, are shared for mutual benefit over time.

Figure 1: MaDiTraCe engagement overview

MaDiTraCe's activities and initiatives will be geared towards identifying the challenges affecting the raw materials and mining sectors in their own territories of action, considering the opportunities they will bring for the creation of new value chains focused on traceability, sustainability and transparency.

The project also involves a multi-stakeholder engagement process, involving both upstream and downstream industrial stages, from mining to manufacturing. This engagement includes the active participation of large networks through the consortium, an international team of universities, institutes, industrial partners, and a cluster.

Figure 2: MaDiTraCe stakeholders' community

Continuous dialogue and consensus building with this stakeholder community on traceability technologies and the certification system developed under the project will ensure alignment with industrial needs and expectations, especially in terms of regulatory

compliance. In addition, this approach will facilitate the adoption, implementation and exploitation of the project results.

To achieve this, the project has defined a specific task for the identification, management, and involvement of stakeholders in the frame of the project: Task 1.1 - WP1.

2 MaDiTraCe ecosystem

MaDiTraCe primary ecosystem (Figure 3) is composed of 14 entities which represent 7 EU countries. The consortium is composed by 3 universities, 3 public research institutions, 6 technological companies, 1 cluster and 1 European institute. Those entities will promote cross-sectoral exchange of knowledge and ideas, linking different European territories through collaboration that share their own environments and thus enrich the process itself.

Figure 3: MaDiTraCe Ecosystem

Participating partners and the continuous interaction between numerous stakeholders from the mining industry to the manufacturing industry, as well as large networks through consortia (EIT-RM) and the cluster (ISMC), make MaDiTrace a firm intent.

The industry and policy community on traceability technology come together to lead the way towards honest and reliable raw materials traceability and as a result, in the development of certification schemes considering the needs and expectations of the industry in terms of regulatory compliance.

On this behalf, the value of the consortium multiplies the chances of success of the project and therefore, it is necessary to establish an outline of MaDiTraCe related projects, initiatives and events that favour its growth, increase its visibility and create synergies at all levels.

2.1 Topics covered by MaDiTraCe

Since MaDiTraCe's main objective is to expand and integrate the portfolio of technology solutions by strengthening the reliability of CRM tracking and transparency of complex supply chains, the development of new approaches to traceability is key as well as the pursuit of opportunities through relevant initiatives and projects related to the main themes of the project, encompassing all mineral supply chains, from mine to manufactured and recycled products.

Therefore, there are three main topics on which MaDiTraCe is based: traceability, sustainability, transparency.

Figure 4: MaDiTraCe main topics & application range.

These pillars are key to identifying projects, activities and events related to MaDiTraCe because:

- **Traceability:** MaDiTraCe will demonstrate the potential of **material fingerprinting** and artificial tagging as independent mechanisms for supporting mineral traceability procedures and claims as they pertain to cobalt, lithium, natural graphite, and rare earth elements. This will be achieved through the full digitalisation of document-based traceability enabled by **DPP** technology, a blockchain-based means of storing decentralised and digitally verifiable data.
- **Sustainability:** As companies face stringent demands for transparency, traceability and sustainability in the manufacturing of their products, they require reliable information from producers about the **origin of their raw materials, processes and compliance with regulation**. Besides, **circular economy** in CRM aims to reduce waste by providing businesses with a new framework for sustainable production and manufacturing, therefore, solid data is also needed to conduct carbon footprint studies and for performance improvement.
- **Transparency:** The project will provide complete coverage of the supply chains of the four CRM from exploration, mining and processing to labelling final products and recycling post-consumer products. Hereto, a **certification system** will be developed in the CERA project funded by EIT Raw Materials. This end-to-end system considers the entire mineral value chain and will aim to streamline the certification landscape for mineral raw materials. In this way, industry players and consumers can count on one complete certification system.

In short, MaDiTraCe will bring technological and innovation solutions for the blockchain implementation within the sectors involved: ICT, circular economy, efficiency/sustainability, green technology, manufacturing and, transport/storage. Consequently, it will be a priority to consider and seek opportunities at relevant events related to the challenges (Figure 5) of these sectors to share the project ideas and reinforce the necessary technological system deployment throughout the value chain.

Figure 5: Raw Materials & Mining sector main challenges

3 Projects related to the topics identified

Below, three tables have been created with the related projects that would help to promote MaDiTraCe and to create synergies among the experts. Each table responds to the type of call and funding the project receives: projects funded by the EU, projects from the EIT RM call, and other projects responding to other criteria, such as from national agencies. This will allow the exchange of knowledge and experience for the mutual benefit of all projects. As can be seen, some of them have been completed and others are ongoing, but both are interesting options for the consortium to establish new proposals or share results. Also, throughout the life of MaDiTraCe, some potential projects may be dropped, and new ones may be added.

Project funded by European Union					
Related project (name)	Level of impact	Call, reference and time of execution (if applicable)	MaDiTraCe partners involved	Related topic	Description of the project
SCRREEN: Solutions for CRITICAL Raw materials - a European Expert Network http://www.screenlab.eu/index.html	European	H2020-SC5-2016-2017 GA 730227 2016-2019	BRGM, CEA	CRM	The project animates and develops a network of experts that seek to provide advice and support the commission in in policy making related to CRMs in general or linked to specific applications or sectors. This network can support and provide relevant data to MaDiTraCe.
Re-Sourcing: Responsible Solutions for Responsible Sourcing https://re-sourcing.eu/	European	H2020-SC5-2018-2019-2020 GA 869276 2019-2023	EIT RM, MUL	CRM	RE-SOURCING is an EU-funded Multi-Stakeholder Platform that aims to advance Responsible Sourcing of raw materials along and across global mineral value chains. RE-SOURCING is developing visions & roadmaps for the three key sectors of Renewable Energy, Mobility and Electric & Electronic Equipment.
SCRREEN 2: Synergic Circular Economy across European Region 2 https://screen.eu/	European	H2020-LOW-CARBON-CIRCULAR-INDUSTRIES-2020 GA 958211 2020-2023	BRGM, CEA, EIT RM, GTK, LGI, Leiden University	CRM	Based on the experience and background of SCRREEN, the prolongation of the project SCRREEN2 will continue to develop and animate an Expert Network which will contribute to expert advice in support of decision-making at the EU level covering all the raw materials and their value chains screened in the CRMs assessment.
FutuRaM: Securing the supply of secondary & critical raw material in the EU. https://futuram.eu/	International	HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01 GA 101058522 2022 - 2026	BRGM, GTK, Leiden University	CRM	FutuRaM will develop the Secondary Raw Materials knowledge base on the availability and recoverability of secondary raw materials (SRMs) within the European Union (EU), with a special focus on critical raw materials (CRMs).

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S34I: Secure and Sustainable Supply of Raw Materials for EU Industry https://s34i.eu/	European	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01 GA 101091616 2023 - 2025	ICAMCYL, ISMC, GTK, LGI	CRM	S34I will research and innovate new data-driven methods to analyse Earth Observation (EO) data, supporting systematic mineral exploration and continuous monitoring of extraction, closure and post closure activities with the aim to increase European autonomy regarding raw materials (RM) resources.
CIRCTHREAD: Building the Digital Thread for Circular Economy Product, Resource & Service Management https://circthread.com/	European	H2020 CE-SC5-31-2020 GA 958448 2021-2025	NA	Traceability	The objective is to interconnect the information along the life of a product, from concept to retirement, so that it can be easily accessed and shared. This will allow you and others to make decisions at all stages to shift to a circular economy.
CE-RISE: Circular Economy Resource Information System https://ce-rise.eu/	European	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-01 GA 101092281 2023-2026	BRGM, Leiden University	Traceability	The Circular Economy Resource Information System (CE-RISE) project aims to create an information system and integrate digital product passports, that will share detailed information on electronic products.
EIS: Exploration Information System https://eis-he.eu/	European	HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01 GA 101057357 2022 -2025	BRGM, GTK, LGI	Traceability	EIS aims to develop innovative exploration concepts and data analysis tools to secure new sources of CRM for the EU's economy.
MIXMATTERS https://mixmatters.eu	European	HORIZON-JU-CBE-2022 GA 101112409 2023-2027	FUNDITEC	Traceability	MixMatters proposes an innovative system that efficiently separates and valorises three types of mixed bio-waste streams containing impurities from the agri-food industry and obtains six high value-added outputs. The system functioning is optimised via a Decision Support while transparency and traceability are ensured via a Digital Product Passport.
CIRPASS- Digital Product Passport https://cirpassproject.eu/	European	Digital Programme Europe	CEA	Traceability	The aim of CIRPASS is to prepare the ground for a gradual deployment of DPPs, with an initial focus on the electronics, batteries and textile sectors. the work

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		GA 101083432 2022-2024			done as part of the CIRPASS project can serve as a good basis for MaDiTraCe project on everything related to DPP.
Trace4EU	European	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure project 2023-2025	Spherity	Traceability	Trace4EU aims to build a common technical ground for the traceability of documents and physical goods using the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
AfricaMaVal: Building EU-Africa Partnerships on Sustainable Raw Materials Value Chain https://africamaval.eu/	International	HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01 GA 101057832 2022-2025	BRGM, DMT, EIT RM, LGI	Transparency	Develops EU-Africa partnership on responsible sourcing of mineral resources for the EU industry while granting a sustainable local co-development.
TransensusLCA: Towards a European-wide harmonised, transport specific LCA Approach	European	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D5-01-04 - LCA GA 101056715 2022-2025	BRGM, Leiden University	Transparency	TransensusLCA aims to develop a baseline for a European-wide harmonised, commonly accepted and applied single life cycle assessment (LCA) approach for a zero-emission road transport system. BRGM participate in mineral resources tasks.
TARANTULA: Recovery of Tungsten, Niobium and Tantalum occurring as by-products in mining and processing waste streams https://h2020-tarantula.eu/	European	H2020-SC5-2018-2019-2020 GA 821159 2019 - 2023	ICAMCYL	Sustainability	Recovery of Tungsten, Niobium and Tantalum occurring as by-products in mining and processing waste streams.
Biorecover: https://biorecover.eu/	European	H2020-SC5-2018-2019-2020 GA 821096 2020 - 2023	LGI	Sustainability	Identify detailed characteristics and establish a conditioning procedure for each raw material to maximise the biorecovery process.
ROBINSON: Smart integRation Of local energy sources and innovative storage for flexiBle, secure and cost-	European	H2020-LC-SC3-ES-4-2018-2020	FUNDITEC	Sustainability	ROBINSON's main mission is to develop an integrated energy system to help decarbonise islands. The system, which will be demonstrated on the island of Eigerøy, Norway, couples locally available energy

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efficient eEnergy Supply ON industrialized islands www.robinson-h2020.eu		GA 957752 2020-2024			sources, electrical and thermal networks and storage technologies, using hydrogen as energy carrier.
PASSENGER: developing sustainable rare-earth-free permanent magnets https://passenger-project.eu/	European	H2020-SC5-2020- GA 101003914 2021 - 2025	EIT RM, ICAMCYL	Sustainability	PASSENGER is developing an innovative way to produce permanent magnets without rare-earth materials and is piloting the new magnets in one of the most crucial fields for the European green economy: the electromobility sector.
GR4FITE3: Graphite Resilience For lithium-Ion baTtery anodes through a sustainable European End-to-End supply chain. https://gr4fite3.eu/	International	HORIZON-CL5-2022- D2-01 GA 101103752 2023-2027	BRGM	Sustainability	GR4FITE3 aims to reach Graphite Resilience For lithium-Ion battery anodes through a sustainable European End-to-End supply chain.
BATMASS: EU circular BATtery valley for second life, recycling, and re-manufacturing of materials and black MASS	European	I3-2021-INV1 GA 101115058 2023-2025	ISMC	Sustainability	BATMASS aims to implement the first EU Circular Battery Valley. It offers a portfolio of cross-regional investments of innovations in circular technologies and processes for battery materials. BATMASS mobilizes an integrated interregional ecosystem around 4 Demonstrators (or 'Demo lighthouses') meant to scale up, commercialize and deploy breakthrough GreenTech.
MetroCycleEU: Metrology for the recycling of technology critical elements to support Europe's circular economy agenda. https://www.metrocycle.eu/	European	EMPIR CALL 2020- INDUSTRY, FUNDAMENTAL, NORMATIVE, SUPPORT FOR NETWORKS & SUPPORT FOR IMPACT 2021-2024	BRGM, MUL	Sustainability	The aim of this project is to develop new methods for TCE measurements in urban mine waste and other environmental relevant matrix, giving industry and authorities a more robust framework for the sustainable usage of these elements. It is an opportunity to discuss the protocol of preparation and analysis of batteries and cathode active material.

Table 1: Projects funded by EU

Projects funded by EIT RM					
Related project (name)	Level of impact	Call, reference and time of execution (if applicable)	MaDiTraCe partners involved	Related topic	Description of the project
CERA4in1: Certification of Raw Materials https://www.cera4in1.org/	International	EIT RM program 2019	DMT, MUL, Leiden University	Traceability	CERA 4in1 will be the first universal and comprehensive certification scheme that accommodates all minerals and all regions. MaDiTraCe will continue development of the CERA 4in1 certification scheme for sustainable raw materials to cover the full raw material supply chain.
CSyARES: Blockchain based Circular system for Assessing Rare Earth Sustainability https://www.circularise.com/public-projects/circular-system-for-assessing-rare-earth-sustainability	European	EIT RM program Call for KAVA 8 Upscaling projects GA 21084 2022-2025	NA	Transparency	CSyARES creates a standardised sustainability certification for rare earth elements (REE), focusing on a "Product Environmental Footprint". The project intends to integrate REIA's sustainability standards for REE with Circularise's patented traceability technology and Minviro's sustainability metrics.
Solsa DEM'UP https://solsa-dem-up.eu/en/our-journey/ongoing-eit-raw-materials-solsa-demup-project	European	EIT RM program 2022-2025	BRGM	Sustainability	The concept is based on integrated drilling coupled with an automated scanner and phase identification software, piloting various analytical instruments and interpreting the results in real time.
HiQ-LCA https://hiq-lca.eu/	European	EIT RM Program KAVA Call 10 Lighthouse Appendix GA 22039 2023 - 2025	BRGM, Leiden University	Sustainability	HiQ-LCA will build a battery LCA database and related battery-specific services for companies who are operating along the value chain and who want to reliably determine the carbon footprint of their processes and products due to the new Battery Regulation of the EU.

Table 2: Projects funded by EIT RM

Other national and international projects					
Related project (name)	Level of impact	Call, reference and time of execution (if applicable)	MaDiTraCe partners involved	Related topic	Description of the project
Ofremi: French observatory for critical raw materials https://www.brgm.fr/en/news/press-release/launching-ofremi-french-observatory-mineral-resources	National	NA 2022	BRGM	CRM	Involving public authorities and the main industrial sectors, it will provide its partners with a strategic, economic, and technical watch on global supply chains and the current and future needs of the industrial sector in order to produce the risk analyses needed for any investment decision.
Australia battery research hub	Australia	Australian R&D funds	NA	CRM	Development of a trusted supply chain for Australian battery minerals and products.
SmartACV	National	NA	CEA	Traceability	This project focuses on improving the trust of current LCA with a focus on LCA for batteries. One of the project goals is to leverage DPPs and a blockchain system to carry dynamic LCAs.
Reacteur numérique	National	NA 2020-2024	CEA	Traceability	This project aims at ensuring the traceability of scientific model-based approach supported by smart contracts.
BATTRACE: Developing new technologies for the traceability and sustainable production of battery raw materials	International	Co-research project, funded by Business Finland 2020 - 2023	GTK	Traceability	Material fingerprinting methodology is developed for lithium, graphite, and cobalt-nickel. Geochemical reference library is compiled for these commodities. Business models related to traceability of battery minerals are evaluated.
Sustainable minerals: Traceability https://www.nordicinnovation.org/programs/sustainable-minerals-traceability	European	Sustainable Minerals program launched by the five Nordic ministers of trade and industry 2022 - 2024	GTK	Traceability	The overall objective is to develop a whole-chain traceability technique (GeoPass) for rare earths and basalt fibers produced in the Nordic countries.

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Conflict Free Tin Initiative (CFTI) https://www.resolve.ngo/site-cfti/default.htm?RD=1	National	NA 2012-2014	NA	Traceability	This is a project focused on solutions to "conflict minerals" problems. The project will implement of traceability systems for the formalization of mining.
Battery Pass: Sustainable impact on the EU battery passport ecosystem https://thebatterypassport.eu/	European	German Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Actions GA BZF335	NA	Traceability	Battery Passport content guidance and implementation.
ESPADIN	National	CDTI-Spain 2022-2024	FUNDITEC	Traceability	Novel use of the design and implementation of European Data Spaces for interoperability and trust in the use of data for the new 4.0 industry. FUNDITEC supports the design of the system architecture and covers the implementation of a traceability toolkit for auditing and certifying renewable energy production and usage.
AGRISOL	National	NA	FUNDITEC	Traceability	Novel use of the design and implementation of European Data Spaces for traceability of energetic conditions in greenhouse environments regulated by certain specific variables as temperature. FUNDITEC supports the design of the system architecture and covers the implementation of a traceability toolkit for auditing and certifying renewable energy production and usage.
BATCircle2.0: Finland-based circular ecosystem of battery metals consortium https://batcircle.aalto.fi/en	European	Co-innovation project, funded by Business Finland 2021 - 2023	GTK	Sustainability	Reference materials for nickel, lithium and cobalt in various forms (e.g., drill core, run-of-mine ore and concentrate) are developed and characterized. A plan to produce reference materials for e-waste is assessed. Methodology of using Li isotopes in loose spodumene pegmatite boulders as an exploration tool is developed and evaluated.

Table 3: Other national and international projects

4 Activities & Events related to the topics identified

4.1 National, European & international initiatives

Considering that consortia will disseminate MaDiTraCe its actions and its results in different initiatives, not only at international level but also national, the following table has been created according to the information provided by the project partners.

Name	Type of initiative	Sector	Level of impact	Relation with the topics
EU Critical Raw Materials Act	EU legal framework	Legal	European Union	Direct implementation tool of the EU CRM Act, related to standardization and certification of sustainable raw materials.
EU Batteries Regulation	EU legal framework	Legal	European Union	Direct implementation tool of the EU Batteries Regulation, related to standardization and certification of sustainable battery raw materials.
Horizon Europe Batt4EU	EU Innovation Action	Innovation and industry	European Union	BATT4EU is a Co-programmed Partnership established under Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union- that aims to achieve a competitive and sustainable European industrial value-chain for e-mobility and stationary applications.
Global Battery Alliance (GBA)	Industry association	Industry	International	The GBA conceptualized the Battery Passport as a framework to increase transparency across the battery value chain. Several participants of the project are in relation with GBA and are involved in other initiatives.
Catena-X	Industry association	Industry	German / European	The Catena-X battery passport is a key enabler for a circular economy. Sharing of supply chain data in automotive supply chain.
World Economic Forum's Mining and Metals Industry Community (WEF)	Industry community	Industry	International	The WEF Mining and Metals Industry community is a high-level group of peers dedicated to ensuring the long-term sustainability of their industry and value to society. MU Leoben is in contact with WEF and will try to engage WEF leader to play an active role in the stakeholder process ('Multipliers and Catalysts').
Tracr TM - De Beers Group	Blockchain platform	Innovation	International	Tracr has successfully proven the ability to trace diamonds along the entire value chain. DeBeer's parent company Anglo American has a keen interest in the tracking and tracing of raw materials.

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European innovation partnership (EIP) on raw materials	Stakeholder platform	Industry	European	The European innovation partnership on raw materials is a stakeholder platform that brings together representatives from industry, public services, academia and NGOs. Its mission is to provide high-level guidance to the European Commission, EU countries and private actors on innovative approaches to the challenges related to raw materials.
OECD Mining regions network	Industry platform	Industry	International	The OECD's Mining Cities and Regions Initiative serves as a platform for exchanging good practices and promoting international standards aimed at improving well-being outcomes in mining regions.
Euromines	Industry association	Industry	International	Euromines is the recognised representative of the European metals and minerals mining industry. The association provides services to its members about EU policy and serves as a network for cooperation and for the exchange of information throughout the sector within Europe. It provides a formal platform in which the members evaluate the impact of European and International policies and legislation on the industry and define common positions and actions.
European Technology Platform on Sustainable Mineral Resources (ETP SMR)	Industry platform	Industry	European	The European Technology Platform on Sustainable Mineral Resources aims to develop long-term European Minerals Industries Research and Innovation agendas and roadmaps for action at EU and national level.
European Geological Data Infrastructure (EGDI)	Industry platform	Research	European	EGDI provides access to Pan-European and national geological datasets and services from the Geological Survey Organizations of Europe. EGDI contains results of projects covering a broad range of geoscientific themes.
International Raw Materials Observatory (INTRAW)	Industry association	Research and innovation	International	INTRAW promotes international cooperation on mineral raw materials research and innovation, education and outreach, industry and trade and recycling, management and substitution of strategic raw materials as well as, disseminates best practice on mineral raw materials supply.
Raw Materials Information System (RMIS)	EU information portal	Research and innovation	European	The European Commission's (EC) Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) is developed by the Directorate-General (DG) Joint Research Centre (JRC) in cooperation with the DG for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (GROWTH). The RMIS is the Commission's reference web-based knowledge platform on non-fuel, non-agricultural raw materials from primary and secondary sources. This section provides an overview of the European raw

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				materials context, the policy mandate that underlies the development of the RMIS, its goal and scope.
European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA)	Industry association	Industry	European	The European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA) aims to make Europe economically more resilient by diversifying its supply chains, creating jobs, attracting investments to the raw materials value chain, fostering innovation, training young talents and contributing to the best enabling framework for raw materials and the Circular Economy worldwide.
Initiative for Responsible Mining Activity (IRMA)	Industry association	Industry	International	IRMA offers true independent assessment against a comprehensive standard for all mined materials that provides 'one-stop coverage' of the full range of issues related to the impacts of industrial-scale mines.
United Nations Economic Commission for Europe - Sustainable resource management (UNECE)	Industry association	Policy	European, international	In 2017, UNECE member States decided to extend UNFC beyond a classification system to a dynamic resource management system that can help countries, organizations, and companies address sustainability challenges. The Expert Group on Resource Management (EGRM) has been tasked to develop the United Nations Resource Management System (UNRMS), a voluntary global standard for integrated and sustainable resource management.
ISO PC Sustainable Raw Materials	EU legal framework	Legal	International	Development of ISO standard for sustainable raw materials on behalf of the European Commission. Support for implementation of the EU CRM Act.

Table 4: Local and international initiatives

4.2 European and International Events

The following table just presents the events that, in the moment of this report submission (M9), are available in the calendar. This means that this list is not closed and will be filled with more information throughout the life project.

Name	Date	Places	Description
World mining congress	26/06/2023 29/06/2023 2024 TBC	Brisbane, Australia	The World Mining Congress 2023, Brisbane, Australia events have set the scene for international agreements and high-level discussions that have influenced mining practices and the resource industry for decades. It is an opportunity to join senior mining industry owners, investors, national and international government representatives, researchers, educators, regulators, suppliers and operators from around the world.

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RE-SOURCING Conference 2023	21/09/2023 22/09/2023	Vienna, Austria	The conference will present and leverage the key results of RE-SOURCING project for setting a future work agenda on responsible sourcing in mineral value chains. The conference will adopt a systemic lens in interactive sessions participants will work together towards a common understanding of root causes and hot spots inhibiting needed systemic change
EU industry days 2023	04/10/2023 05/10/2023	Málaga, Spain	The EU Industry Days are Europe's flagship annual event focussing on key industrial policy discussions, connecting industrial frontrunners, and boosting the knowledge base of European industry.
EU SUPERCLUSTER LAPLAND GEOCONFERENCE	30/10/2023 31/10/2023	Rovaniemi, Finland	Clustering event to discuss and exchange ideas on current technological challenges and topics within the Raw Material sector.
Fennoscandian Exploration and Mining	31/10/2023 02/11/2023	Levi, Finland	FEM Conference focuses on exploration and mining. FEM invites speakers from exploration and mining companies, research institutes, academia, authorities and geological surveys
EU Raw Materials Week 2023	13/11/2023 17/11/2023	Brussels, Belgium	The Raw Materials Week is an annual event organised by the European Commission. It gathers a wide range of stakeholders discussing policies and initiatives in the field of raw material, providing an overview of ongoing EU activities in this sector.
XV International congress of mining and mineral resources	22/11/2023 24/11/2023	León, Spain	The XV International Congress on Energy and Mineral will bring together more than 400 professionals/150 companies, students and technicians from the sector to discuss topics of common interest.
Resourcing Tomorrow 2023	28/11/2023 30/11/2023	London, United Kingdom	Resourcing Tomorrow is focused on accelerating the energy transition. The Resourcing Tomorrow Theatre will cover the energy transition, environmental resilience, decarbonisation, ESG, and critical minerals.
International round table on materials criticality IRTC	21/2/2024 23/2/2024	Torino, Italy	IRTC, the "International Round Table on Materials Criticality" is a project established in 2018 and funded by EIT Raw Materials. IRTC consists of leading international experts in material criticality discussing different perspectives and requirements of criticality assessments, impacts of criticality, and ways to mitigate it. The project bridges academic expertise, industry practice, and policy-making, and engages with stakeholders around the world.
Euro Mine Expo	28/05/2024 30/05/2024	Skellefteå, Sweden	International trade fair and conference for the mining industry. Cutting edge innovations and the latest methods in mining.
Mining Forum	06/06/2024 07/06/2024	Berlin, Germany	International networking conference for the mining and raw materials sector, bringing together the industry's top decision makers, experts and specialists every two years to discuss topics related to mining and associated fields, such as tunnelling and geophysics.

D5.4 Report on identification of related projects and activities

International Meeting on Lithium Batteries 2024 (IMLB)	16/06/2024 21/06/2024	Stuttgart, Germany	IMLB is the premier international conference on the state of lithium battery science and technology, as well as current and future related battery systems for application in transportation, industry, grid storage, aviation, aerospace, biomedical, and other promising sectors.
FORUM ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT mining-metallurgical	17/06/2024 19/06/2024	Madrid, Spain	Mining-metallurgical forum on sustainable development showcases a variety of industry equipment, technology, and related products for the mining sector and beyond.
FUTURE OF MINING, Sydney	18/03/2024 19/03/2024	Sydney, Australia	Future of Mining Australia is focused to learn, challenge and debate with region's pioneering innovators to address new solutions and shape a bullet-proof strategy that hits the operational goals.
PDAC Convention	03/03/2024 06/03/2024	Toronto, Canada	The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention is the leading event for people, companies and organizations connected to mineral exploration. The annual award winning PDAC Convention in Toronto, Canada brings together up to 30,000 attendees from over 130+ countries for its educational programming, networking events and business opportunities.
BAUMA	07/04/2025 13/04/2025	Munich, Germany	World's Leading Trade Fair for Construction Machinery, Building Material Machines, Mining Machines, Construction Vehicles and Construction Equipment.

Table 5: Related events

5 Conclusions

Throughout this report, multiple initiatives, projects, and events have been described to ensure the coordination and cooperation of partners as well as to guarantee the growth and success of MaDiTraCe in terms of transparency, sustainability, and traceability for the certification of CRM in the EU. In this sense, the identification of possible avenues of impact and cooperation will be an ongoing activity in the MaDiTraCe project and aims at establishing reliable communication and collaboration with relevant experts, stakeholders, and projects to detect possible contributions previously unidentified, to enrich this project and the general knowledge on CRM. This topic is becoming a critical and strategic issue for many countries and many initiatives and projects are emerging, therefore, as mentioned before, the list included in this report is not exhaustive.

As one of the key aspects of MaDiTraCe is to achieve strong industry support for the implementation of the DPP, based on new blockchain technologies, this will require significant dissemination and communication work including initiatives at all levels, but most importantly those that are committed to international synergies, as well as the identification of areas for improvement in future activities.

Finally, the commitment of all work WPs will be of vital importance in identifying the challenges of the raw materials and mining sector in their own territories of action, considering the opportunities for the creation of new value chains.

